

Supplementary Material: SMT-based Translation Validation for Machine Learning Compiler

This is a supplementary material of SMT-based Translation Validation for Machine Learning Compiler (CAV'22).

1 SMT Encoding of Commutative Functions

For any binary and commutative function $f(x, y)$ whose domain and range are bit-vectors, we can find f' such that $\forall x, y. f(x, y) = f'(x, y) \& f'(y, x)$ where $\&$ is a bitwise-and operation. This is done by defining f' as follows.

1. If $x \leq y$, $f'(x, y) = f(x, y)$.
2. If $x > y$, $f'(x, y) = 11\dots 11_{(2)}$.

Given a predicate P on an uninterpreted and commutative function f , if an SMT solver can find a definition of f that makes the predicate true, the solver can also find a definition of f' which makes predicate P' that is P with all occurrences of $f(x, y)$ replaced with $f'(x, y) \& f'(y, x)$ true. Also, if the solver concludes that there is no f making P true, there is no definition of f' that makes P' true as well.

2 Supporting Multiple FP Types

This sections describes the details of supporting multiple floating-point types that are omitted in the main paper due to the space limit.

2.1 Encoding Extension and Truncation of Floating-Point Numbers

In IEEE-754, floating point numbers of a small type can always be casted into the larger type without loss of precision. The abstract bit-vector value of the extended number is equivalent to concatenation of (1) the sign bit, (2) zero bits for limit bits (LB), (3) the magnitude bits of the source (abstract) value for truncated bits (TB), and (4) zero bits for precision bits (PB). The expression below shows the abstract bit-vector representation of the extended value of f .

$$\llbracket extend(f) \rrbracket = \text{sign}(\llbracket f \rrbracket) \text{ ++ } 00..0 \text{ ++ } \text{magnitude}(\llbracket f \rrbracket) \text{ ++ } 00..0$$

Casting a floating-point number into a smaller type is complex because the destination type may not have enough precision. To model the rounding behavior, we use an uninterpreted function that decides the rounding direction. The uninterpreted function takes the abstract bit-vector representation of some

floating point number and returns a bit which is 1 if the value is to be ceiled or 0 if to be floored. This is overapproximation because the rounding direction may not be exactly that of IEEE-754. According to this rounding direction, we use TB(floor) or TB+1(ceil) for the truncated MB.

If the number is too big or large, the truncated value is $\pm\infty$. To model this, we check the LB of the source value. If LB is not zero, the result is $\pm\infty$.

2.2 Encoding Constants of Multiple FP Types

To encode constants, we first acquire the casting information for every constant appearing in the source and target function. Casting information tells whether (1) this constant overflows after truncation, (2) requires rounding prior to truncation, and (3) should it be rounded, which direction should it be as well.

Based on the casting information, we fill in LB, TB, and PB of each constant. LB is forced to be zero if the value doesn't overflow, and nonzero if it does. TB is assigned the MB of the floored and truncated value. PB is forced to be zero if the value doesn't require rounding, and nonzero if it does. Then, we add the precondition of the rounding direction UF to encode the actual rounding direction. Finally, we add the preconditions to give the real-world total order between composed bit-vectors.

2.3 Considering Truncated FP Constants

To explain constant folding of casts, the ceiled or floored value of constants are considered as well. First, we extend every constant in the source and target programs to the highest precision type and add them to C which becomes a complete set of truncated FP numbers. For any float type t , $\lfloor c_i \rfloor_t$ and $\lceil c_i \rceil_t$ for any constant c_i appearing in the functions are added to C .

2.4 Calculating the Bit Width for Precise Casting

PB should be at least $\lceil \log_2 N \rceil$ where N is the number of FP variables. It is because all FP registers may store distinct FP numbers that gets truncated to a single FP number. Also, all FP registers may store distinct FP numbers that all get truncated to $\pm\infty$. Therefore, LB + TB + PB should be at least $\lceil \log_2 N \rceil$ as well, which is already satisfied by the bound of PB.

3 Unification of Multiple Hash Functions

This section shows when unifying multiple hash functions into one is okay.

Let's assume there are total p pairs of equality preconditions. Also, let's assume that function f_i is the hash function used in the i^{th} equality precondition. Suppose that $k * f_i := \lambda x . f_i(x) * k$ for some integer k .

Theorem 1. *There exists a_1, a_2, \dots, a_p where $0 \leq a_i \leq i$ that makes $F := a_1 * f_1 + a_2 * f_2 + \dots + a_p * f_p$ satisfy all of the following statements.*

$$\begin{aligned} \text{sum}(A_1) \neq \text{sum}(B_1) &\implies \sum_{x \in A_1} F(x) \neq \sum_{x \in B_1} F(x) \\ \dots \\ \text{sum}(A_p) \neq \text{sum}(B_p) &\implies \sum_{x \in A_p} F(x) \neq \sum_{x \in B_p} F(x) \end{aligned}$$

Proof. We will prove it by induction. Given i , let's assume that we could find a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k that makes the $1 \sim k^{\text{th}}$ statements satisfied. Then, we can always construct new $a'_1, a'_2, \dots, a'_{k+1}$ from the previous values.

Basis. $a_1 = 1$ makes $F := f_1$, which naturally makes the first statement satisfied by an assumption.

Inductive step. Let's assume that we determined a_1, \dots, a_k . The next step is to determine a_{k+1} . If $a_{k+1} = 0$ makes the $(k+1)^{\text{th}}$ statement hold by chance, the proof is completed since $a_{k+1} = 0 \leq k+1$.

If the $(k+1)^{\text{th}}$ statement is not satisfied, increase a_{k+1} by 1. Since f_{k+1} will hash A_{k+1}, B_{k+1} arrays into difference values when $\text{sum}(A_{k+1}) \neq \text{sum}(B_{k+1})$, $\sum_{x \in A_{k+1}} f_{k+1}(x) \neq \sum_{x \in B_{k+1}} f_{k+1}(x)$ holds. Therefore, $a_{k+1} = 1$ makes the $(k+1)^{\text{th}}$ statement satisfied.

However, this may break one of previously satisfied $1 \dots k^{\text{th}}$ statements. Let's say that it is the i^{th} statement that is broken. It means that $\sum_{x \in A_i} F(x) = \sum_{x \in B_i} F(x)$ currently holds. In other words, increasing a_{k+1} affects the hash values of A_i and B_i . This implies that increasing a_{k+1} one more time will again change the equality back to $\sum_{x \in A_i} F(x) \neq \sum_{x \in B_i} F(x)$.

This can happen at most once for each $1 \dots k^{\text{th}}$ statement because we change a_{k+1} in an increasing direction. Therefore, we can determine the value of a_{k+1} that satisfies $1 \dots (k+1)^{\text{th}}$ statements in at most k steps. \square

The range of function F should be $\{x | x \in Z \wedge 0 \leq x \leq p^2\}$ because F is a summation of $a_i * f_i$ where $a_i \leq i$ and f_i is an indicator function. The hash value of an array can be at most $|A| * p^2 = O(|A| * n^4)$.